

Towards the Supply and Demand Process of Mathematics Teachers in Public and Private Secondary Schools

Felix O. Egara
Moeketsi Mosia

Department of Mathematics, Natural Sciences and Technology Education, Faculty of Education,
University of the Free State, Bloemfontein, South Africa

ABSTRACT: This research examined the supply and demand of mathematics teachers in public and private secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone, Nigeria, from 2016 to 2021. The research instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire tagged Reasons Mathematics Teachers Leave the Teaching Profession Questionnaire (RMTLTPQ). The reliability coefficient of the RMTLTPQ obtained was 0.88 using Cronbach's Alpha method. The data collected were analysed using Special Package for Social Science version 23, and descriptive statistics, such as percentages, means, and standard deviation, were used to address the study questions. The hypothesis was tested using t-test statistics with a significance level of 0.05. Findings revealed that: the supply of mathematics teachers in public and private secondary schools does not commiserate with the demand for mathematics teachers; the average mathematics teacher-student ratio in public and private secondary schools in the Zone are 1:234 and 1:298 respectively; the reasons mathematics teachers leave the teaching profession in secondary schools is due to retirement, resignation, irregular and poor remuneration and transfer of service; and a significant difference does not exist between the number of qualified mathematics teachers in the public and private secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone. Based on the findings, recommendations were proffered.

Keywords: Mathematics, Mathematics Teacher, Private and Public Secondary Schools, Mathematics Teachers' Demands, Mathematics Teachers' Supply.

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1. Introduction

Mathematics is needed in every facet of life and at all levels. Mathematics education is vital for any student in their chosen field of study (Egara, 2021; Okeke et al., 2023). It is of everyday use to the educated and uneducated in all nooks and crannies of the earth (Nzeadibe et al., 2020; Osakwe et al., 2022). Homemakers, traders, farmers, tailors, doctors, engineers, clerks and people of all trades and professions need to apply some

knowledge of mathematics every minute of their lives (Inweregbugh et al., 2020; Uka & Ezech, 2022). Mathematics frees the mind and allows people to gauge their intellectual prowess and determine where to develop (Egara & Mosimege, 2024, 2023; Mosimege et al., 2024, Solomon & Oyem, 2021). Mathematics is one of the basic subjects that must be studied by all pupils up to the higher levels of education, according to the Federal Government of Nigeria's National Policy on Education (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2013; Egara & Mosimege, 2023; Egara & Mosimege, 2023b, 2023a, 2024a, 2023d, 2024c). The priority given to mathematics in the primary and secondary school curricula appropriately reflects the crucial role that the discipline plays in modern society (Egara et al., 2021; Mosimege & Egara, 2023b, 2023a; Maruta et al., 2022; Nzeadibe et al., 2023; Okeke et al., 2023).

However, it is sad that students' performance in mathematics in internal and external examinations has remained continuously low, given the subject's relative importance (Egara et al., 2023; Egara et al., 2018, 2021; Maruta et al., 2022; Nzeadibe et al., 2020, 2019). Mathematics researchers over the years have reiterated the factors responsible for students' poor performance in mathematics to include; ineffective teaching methods, lack of instructional materials, overcrowded classes, lack of qualified mathematics teachers, and mathematics anxiety, among others (Egara et al., 2018; Jeje et al., 2019; Okeke et al., 2023; Okeke et al., 2022; Sarfo et al., 2020, 2022; Tarteer & Mukh, 2022; Terry et al., 2023). In this study, the researchers are interested in overcrowded classrooms dominated by students and the inadequacy of qualified mathematics teachers.

Overcrowded mathematics classroom is a problem worldwide for effective teaching and learning process. Large class sizes, a high student-teacher ratio, and insufficient learner space are all signs of an overcrowded classroom (Egara, 2010; Ojonubah, 2015; Ojonubah & Buari, 2011; Osakwe et al., 2023). In the scenario outlined by Ahmad et al. (2018), a crowded classroom contains more pupils than necessary, which impedes teaching and learning. In a classroom setting, overcrowding leads to several other issues, including (i) students not receiving the necessary attention; (ii) teachers being overburdened with the additional workload of extra students to teach; (iii) more papers to grade; and (iv) students who need help waiting several minutes before the teacher can assist them because all the other students must be attended to as well; and (v) the higher student-teacher ratio, the less effective instruction will be (Ojonubah, 2015).

For secondary schools, a teacher-to-student ratio 1:40 was suggested in the National Policy on Education of the Federal Government of Nigeria (2013). A teacher-to-student ratio of 1:40 was also advised by the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) (Waita et al., 2016). One might anticipate rigorous adherence to this guideline by these reputable bodies in light of this universally acknowledged premise. A study by Thomas and Mbwas (2014) on the teacher-to-student ratio reported that a high average teacher-student ratio of 1:233 was observed, which implies one teacher to roughly 213 students. This goes against Nigeria's National Policy on Education, which called for a teacher-to-student ratio of 1:40.

On the contrary, is this recommendation adhered to by schools in Enugu State, especially in Nsukka Education Zone? The following issues must be addressed for the

student-teacher ratio policy to be successfully implemented: insufficient funding, inadequate infrastructure, poor quality assurance organisations, a lack of political will, corruption, teacher shortage, and a lack of qualified mathematics teachers (Chukwu, 2011a; Ogunode & Ahaotu, 2020). The lack of qualified mathematics instructors in the educational system is another cause of students' poor math performance (Tarteer & Mukh, 2022; Thomas & Mbwas, 2014).

A qualified mathematics teacher in this study holds the following certificate such as Nigerian Certificate of Education (NCE), Bachelor of Science Education (B.Sc. (Ed)), Masters in Education (MED) and Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D) in mathematics from a recognised university or college of education in Nigeria. Before being allowed to teach mathematics, a trained teacher must hold a B.Sc. (Ed.) degree at the very least. How well secondary learners learn, comprehend, and perform in mathematics is determined mainly by the kind of mathematics teachers they have, whether they attend public or private schools (Thomas & Mbwas, 2014). This is because educated and adequately employed math instructors should be able to instruct students successfully, resulting in successful learning and better performance. However, when the teachers lack the necessary credentials, they will find it difficult to teach effectively, severely impacting the student's knowledge and performance in mathematics. Unfortunately, Nigerian learners are suffering from the issue of ineffective instruction because the school system is reportedly struggling with several problems, such as a severe scarcity of highly competent mathematics teachers (Thomas & Mbwas, 2014).

However, there is no doubt that well-qualified mathematics teachers are in great demand (Karigi et al., 2015). Hassan (2013) examines factors influencing teacher attrition in public secondary schools in Kabul, Afghanistan. Hassan discovered that the attrition of teachers in Afghanistan is caused by a combination of social factors, a lack of professional development opportunities, low salaries, ineffective recruitment and deployment procedures (due to the distance between the schools), a heavy workload, unequal work distribution, and administrative corruption. Nwakonobi and Obiagwu (2010) found that transfers of service, retirement, low pay, and resignation are the primary grounds for teachers leaving the teaching profession in Anambra State, Nigeria. Has there been a case of demanding qualified mathematics teachers where the supply does not commiserate with the enrolment of secondary school students in the Nsukka Education Zone of Enugu State? In answering this question, the researchers are interested in determining if qualified mathematics teachers are inherent in the public and private secondary schools and also examine the state of mathematics teachers demanded and supplied in public and private secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone between 2016 and 2021.

The demand for teachers refers to the number of teachers required to take up the teaching appointment in a given educational institution(s) and academic season (Alochere, 2013). Teacher demand is the system's required number of teachers (Rai et al., 2017). Similarly, Shittu and Olubor (2021) refer to the demand for teachers as the number needed in schools according to the recommended teacher-student ratio, even when not supplied. Therefore, mathematics teacher demand is the number of qualified mathematics teachers required or needed in the school system, whether public or private, to produce a specific

output in the educational system. Several factors influence the demand for teachers in the school system. The main determinants of teacher demand are the number of teachers who leave the system through retirements, resignation, retrenchments or deaths, increase in learners' enrolment, illnesses and transfer (Shittu & Olubor, 2021). The demand for mathematics teachers can only be met if there are adequate supply of teachers, especially in mathematics.

According to Jano (2013), the supply of teachers refers to the number of individuals who acquired the skills necessary to qualify and are willing to provide teaching services given specific incentives. Alochere (2013) refers to the supply of teachers as those currently working as teachers and those potentially available to be employed in the school system. Rai et al. (2017) see the supply of teachers as the number of qualified or eligible people teaching in the public education system under prevailing conditions of service. Therefore, mathematics teacher supply refers to the number of qualified mathematics teachers employed in public and private education, whether in secondary or primary schools.

In relating the concept of supply to education, Babalola (2003) argued that prices, such as salaries, were determined the same way as the prices of goods. However, given that teacher training takes a relatively long time, it is challenging for market forces to offer an instant solution to the teacher supply problem. Most instructors in Nigeria are deemed to be underpaid and unmotivated (Shittu & Olubor, 2021). These could be seen as issues influencing the supply of teachers in Nigeria, such as teacher absenteeism, chilly classroom procedures, frustration, a deterioration in professional standards, militancy, and early retirement from the teaching profession (Shittu & Olubor, 2021). Ibadin (2010) posited while examining the supply of teachers in secondary schools that the current economic problem in the country had worsened the problem of teacher supply. The teacher supply problem is not concerned with mere numbers but with the quantity necessary for effective utilisation. Ali in Shittu and Olubor (2021) revealed that the percentage increase in yearly enrolments of students was greater than the increase in teacher supply in the educational sector. Considering the increase in students' enrolment, the problem was whether the demand for mathematics teachers had been met by the supply in public and private secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone of Enugu State, Nigeria.

2. Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the demand and supply theory propounded by Adam Smith (founding father of economics) in 1776. The author of the well-known book "The Wealth of Nations" discussed his opinions on markets and how they work. Smith claimed that the invisible hand controls how consumers and producers behave in his writing about the price system, which is based on the theories of supply and demand. Smith Considered the following suppositions: (i) The higher the demand, the lower the price of products and services; (ii) The higher the price, the lower the demand; (iii) The higher the price, the higher the supply; and (iv) The lower the price, the lower the supply. Therefore, it implies that; if the wages of mathematics teachers are low, the higher the demand for their services by their employers. And the higher the wages or salaries of mathematics teachers, the more willing they will be to offer their services. Therefore, to meet the demand and supply of

mathematics teachers, there must be an acceptable point between the employers and the teachers to balance the demand and supply of mathematics teachers in the public and private school systems.

3. Reviewed Studies

The following are reviewed empirical studies related to this study. For instance, Nwakonobi and Obiagwu (2010) looked into the supply and demand of instructors for secondary schools in Nigeria's Anambra State based on the type of school. According to their findings, the number of teachers provided to secondary schools in Anambra State was minimal and well below what was required. In the study conducted by Chukwu (2011b) on the extent of implementation of the Universal Basic Education scheme in the South-East Zone of Nigeria in terms of teacher demand and supply, the finding revealed a small extent of implementation of the scheme in terms of teacher demand and supply, which has negative implications as quality instructional delivery would continue to suffer in primary schools in the South-East Zone. Alochere (2013) examined the demand and supply of vocational and technical subject teachers in technical colleges in Cross River States, Nigeria. Alochere's findings revealed that students' enrolment in technical colleges in the States increased considerably throughout the years of study (2006 to 2010). Alochere's findings also discovered that the supply of technical and vocational teachers had not matched their demand in a technical college. Donita-Schmidt and Zuzovsky (2014) researched the teacher shortage in Israel from the perspective of the schools. They discovered a constant need for teachers throughout the academic year and a balance between supply and demand at the start of the academic year. They also indicated that principals often employ methods to meet the demand by recruiting teachers ineligible for certification or with insufficient training and using temporary teachers for extended periods. In light of their results, the issue of a quantitative teacher shortage is now one of a quality-related hidden shortage. Njau (2017) evaluated the academic achievement of students in secondary schools in Tanzania and the demand for and supply of secondary school instructors. Njau discovered a lack of science and math teachers in government secondary schools. This shortage is due to several factors, including improper staffing, a lack of motivation, a poor work environment, low pay, resignations, retirements, career changes, and the government's failure to hire new teachers.

Another study conducted was the one by Iyomo and Ishola (2018) that examined the demand and supply of technical and vocational education teachers in Ondo State public secondary schools in Nigeria. Iyomo and Ishola's results revealed that between 2009 and 2016, there was a significant relationship between the demand for and supply of vocational education teachers. Their result also showed that with the increase in student enrolment, the demand for vocational education teachers did not match the supply to bring about efficiency in the public secondary schools in Ondo State. In another investigation by Shittu and Olubor (2021), who assessed the demand for and supply of teachers in public Junior Secondary schools in Kwara State, Nigeria, they concluded that the imbalances in the demand for and supply of Junior Secondary School teachers in Kwara State had resulted in overutilisation of teachers, poor students' academic performance and a high rate of examination malpractice among students and teachers. Their result also revealed that there

was a yearly increase in teachers' demand but it was not commensurate with the number of teachers supplied to the schools.

From the reviewed empirical studies above, no study has been conducted to examine the demand and supply of mathematics teachers in the public and private school systems. Therefore, the researchers wish to fill this gap by examining the demand and supply of mathematics teachers in public and private secondary schools in the Nsukka Education Zone of Enugu State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. What is the average number of mathematics teachers that are required by public secondary schools in relation to the number of teachers who retire or leave the teaching profession between 2016 and 2021?
2. What is the average number of mathematics teachers that are required by private secondary schools in relation to the number of teachers who retire or leave the teaching profession between 2016 and 2021?
3. What is the average mathematics teacher-student ratio in public and private secondary schools between 2016 and 2021?
4. What are the reasons that cause mathematics teachers to leave the teaching profession in public and private secondary schools?
5. Does the number of qualified mathematics teachers in the public and private secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone differ?

Hypothesis

1. A difference does not exist between qualified mathematics teachers in the public and private secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone.

4. Methods

This study utilised a descriptive research design. Descriptive design is one in which a selected portion of a population is studied to represent the entire population, allowing a researcher to collect data without manipulation (Nworgu, 2015). The choice of this design was to enable the researchers to get information about the reason that causes mathematics teachers to leave the teaching profession in the public and private secondary school systems.

The population comprised 141 secondary school principals (59 in public and 82 in private) and 254 mathematics teachers (161 in public and 93 in private) in the 141 secondary schools that exist in Nsukka Education Zone of Enugu State (Post Primary School Management Board [PPSMB], 2022; Education Inspectorate Authority [EIA], 2022). Nsukka Education Zone is among the six Education Zones in Enugu State, Nigeria. The six Education Zones are; Agbani Zone, Awgu Zone, Enugu Zone, Nsukka Zone, Obollo-Afor Zone and Udi Zone. Because the population was small and manageable, the researchers used the entire population for the study. However, a purposive sampling technique was used to select Nsukka Education Zone out of the six Zones in the state. This is because

Nsukka Zone is within the researchers' reach. Nsukka Education Zone comprises three Local Government Areas (LGA): Nsukka LGA, Igbo-Etiti LGA and Uzo-Uwani LGA.

The research instrument used for data collection in this study was a questionnaire titled: Reasons Mathematics Teachers Leave the Teaching Profession Questionnaire (RMTLTPQ). The questionnaire was adapted from the questionnaire developed by Nwakonobi and Obiagwu (2010) with a reliability coefficient of 0.72. The adapted instrument is a 5-item questionnaire with a 4-point scale response option of 4 = Strongly Agree (SA), 3 = Agree (A), 2 = Disagree (D), and 1 = Strongly Disagree (SD). The RMTLTPQ was face validated by three experts. A trial testing of the validated RMTLTPQ was conducted on 20 principals and 40 mathematics teachers in public and private secondary schools in another education zone. To determine the internal consistency of the RMTLTPQ, Cronbach's Alpha was used to analyse the data obtained from the trial testing, and the reliability coefficient of the RMTLTPQ obtained was 0.88. The administration of the RMTLTPQ in obtaining the necessary data from the principals and mathematics teachers was done by the researchers, and the process recorded a 100% retrieval of the instrument.

The data collected were analysed using Special Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 28. Descriptive statistics such as percentages, mean (M), and standard deviation (SD) were used to answer the research questions. At the same time, the hypothesis was tested at a 0.05 level of significance using t-test statistics. The average cutoff point utilised from the RMTLTPQ was 2.5. Items with a mean of 3.00 or above imply strongly agree, 2.50 to 2.99 indicates agree, 2.00 to 2.49 denotes disagree, and 1.99 or below implies strongly disagree. In the analysis, "strongly agree" and "agree" were combined to form "Agree", whereas "strongly disagree" and "disagree" were also combined to form "Disagree."

5. Results

The results and data analysis align with the research questions and hypothesis.

Research Question 1: What is the average number of mathematics teachers that are required by public secondary schools in relation to the number of teachers who retire or leave the teaching profession between 2016 and 2021?

Table 1 shows the number of students enrolment, mathematics teacher supply, mathematics teacher-student ratio, mathematics teachers demand (required) and mathematics teachers that retired or left the profession. The data analysis in Table 1 reveals the number of mathematics teachers required by public secondary schools in relation to the number of mathematics teachers who retired or left the teaching profession between 2016 and 2021. From the analysis, an average of 170 mathematics teachers was supplied, representing 17%, as against 820 mathematics teachers required or demanded, representing 83%. Between 2016 and 2021, an average of 4 mathematics teachers retired or left the teaching profession, representing 3% of mathematics teachers in the Zone. Therefore, the researchers concluded that 820 mathematics teachers were the average number that was required or demanded by public secondary schools in relation to the

number of teachers who retired or left the teaching profession in the Nsukka Education Zone between 2016 and 2021.

Table 1: Mathematics teachers demand and supply in public secondary schools from 2016-2021

Year	Student Enrolment	Mathematics Teachers' (MT) Supply	% MT Supply	Math Teacher-Student Ratio (1:40)	Mathematics Teachers' (MT) Demand	% MT Demand	Mathematics teachers that retired or left the profession (Attrition)	% of MT that retired or left (Attrition)
2016	35212	183	21	1:192	697	79	-	-
2017	37576	174	19	1:215	765	81	9	5
2018	39446	169	17	1:233	817	83	5	3
2019	41243	166	16	1:248	865	84	3	2
2020	41949	165	16	1:254	883	84	1	1
2021	42114	161	15	1:261	891	85	4	2
Average	39590	170	17	1:234	820	83	4	3

Source: PPSMB in Nsukka Education Zone and authors' calculations

Note: Students' Enrolment is given, MT Supply is given, and MT Attrition is given.

%MT Supply = MT Supply/MT Demand × 100 (e.g. 183/880 × 100 = 21%,...)

Math Teacher-Student Ratio = Student Enrolment/ MT Supply (e.g. 35212/183 = 192, ⇒ 1:192,...)

MT Demand = (Total Student Enrolment/Desired Student-Teacher Ratio) – MT supply (e.g. 35212/40 = 880-183 = 697,...) *40:1 is the approved/required Student-Teacher Ratio.

%MT Demand =100% – %MT Supply (e.g. 100 - 21 = 79%,...)

%MT Attrition = No. of MT retired or left / MT Supply × 100 (e.g. 9/174 × 100 = 5%,...)

*MT Supply ⇒ Mathematics teachers currently employed and in service.

Figure 1: Chart showing the variation in the demand and supply of mathematics teachers in public secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone of Enugu State from 2016 to 2021

Source: Derived from Table 1.

A thorough look at Figure 1 shows the variations in the demand and supply of mathematics teachers in public secondary schools in the Nsukka Education Zone of Enugu State between 2016 and 2021. The chart reveals great demand for mathematics teachers

compared to the number of mathematics teachers supplied between 2016 and 2021 in the public secondary schools in the Nsukka Education Zone.

Research Question 2: What is the average number of mathematics teachers that are required by private secondary schools in relation to the number of teachers who retire or leave the teaching profession between 2016 and 2021?

Table 2: Mathematics Teachers' Demand and Supply in Private Secondary Schools from 2016-2021

Year	Student Enrolment	Mathematics Teachers' (MT) Supply	% of MT Supply	Math Teacher-Student Ratio (1:40)	Mathematics Teachers' (MT) Demand	% MT Demand	Mathematics teachers that retired or left the profession (Attrition)	% of MT that retired or left (Attrition)
2016	18112	82	18	1:221	371	18	-	-
2017	19642	68	14	1:289	423	32	14	21
2018	21034	59	11	1:357	467	41	9	15
2019	22245	61	11	1:365	495	39	2	3
2020	20496	84	16	1:244	428	16	-	-
2021	23425	75	13	1:312	511	25	10	13
Average	20796	72	14	1:298	449	29	9	13

Source: EIA in Nsukka Education Zone and authors' calculations

Note: Students' Enrolment is given; MT Supply is given; and MT Attrition is given.

%MT Supply = $MT\ Supply / MT\ Demand \times 100$ (e.g. $82/880 \times 100 = 18\%$, ...)

Math Teacher-Student Ratio = $Student\ Enrolment / MT\ Supply$ (e.g. $18112/82 = 221$, $\Rightarrow 1:221$,...)

MT Demand = $(Total\ Student\ Enrolment / Desired\ Student-Teacher\ Ratio) - MT\ supply$ (e.g. $18112/40 = 453-82 = 371$,...) *40:1 is the approved/required student-teacher ratio.

%MT Demand = $100\% - MT\%$ (e.g. $100 - 82 = 18\%$,...)

%MT Attrition = $No.\ of\ MT\ retired\ or\ left / MT\ Supply \times 100$ (e.g. $14/68 \times 100 = 21\%$,...)

*MT Supply \Rightarrow Mathematics teachers currently employed and in service.

Table 2 shows the demand and supply of mathematics teachers in private secondary schools in the Nsukka Education Zone. Table 2 shows the number of students enrolled, mathematics teacher supply, mathematics teacher-student ratio, mathematics teacher demand (required) and mathematics teachers that retired or left the profession. The data analysis in Table 2 reveals the number of mathematics teachers required by private secondary schools in relation to the number of mathematics teachers that retired or left the teaching profession between 2016 and 2021. From the analysis, an average of 72 mathematics teachers was supplied, representing 14%, as against 449 mathematics teachers required or demanded, representing 29%. Between 2016 and 2021, an average of 9 mathematics teachers retired or left the teaching profession representing 13% of mathematics teachers in the Zone. Therefore, the researchers conclude that the average number of mathematics teachers that was required or demanded by private secondary schools in relation to the number of teachers who retired or left the teaching profession in the Nsukka Education Zone between 2016 and 2021 is 449.

Figure 2: Chart showing the variation in the demand and supply of mathematics teachers in private secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone of Enugu State from 2016 to 2021.

Source: Derived from Table 2.

A thorough look at Figure 2 shows the variations in the demand and supply of mathematics teachers in private secondary schools in the Nsukka Education Zone of Enugu State between 2016 and 2021. The chart reveals great demand for mathematics teachers compared to the number of mathematics teachers supplied between 2016 and 2021 in the private secondary schools in the Nsukka Education Zone.

Research Question 3: What is the average mathematics teacher-student ratio in public and private secondary schools between 2016 and 2021?

Analysis from Tables 1 and 2 was used to answer research question 3. Tables 1 and 2 show the mathematics teacher-student ratio from 2016 to 2021. Table 1 shows that the average mathematics teacher-student ratio in public secondary schools between 2016 and 2021 is 1:234. This implies that one mathematics teacher to about two hundred and thirty-four students. Similarly, Table 2 shows that the average mathematics teacher-student ratio in the private secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone between 2016 and 2021 is 1:298. This implies that one mathematics teacher to about two hundred and ninety-eight students.

Research Question 4: What are the reasons that cause mathematics teachers to leave the teaching profession in public and private secondary schools?

Table 3: Reasons mathematics teachers in secondary schools leave the teaching profession by school principals (N=141)

S/N	Item Statement	Public School Principals			Private School Principals		
		Mean	Standard Deviation	Decision	Mean	Standard Deviation	Decision
1	Mathematics teachers leave the profession due to retirement	2.65	.76	Agree	2.15	.85	Disagree
2	Mathematics teachers leave the profession due to resignation	2.54	.87	Agree	3.20	.64	Strongly Agree
3	Mathematics teachers leave the profession due to irregular and poor remuneration	3.14	.70	Strongly Agree	3.55	.53	Strongly Agree
4	Mathematics teachers leave the profession due to transfer of service	2.54	.75	Agree	1.83	.75	Strongly disagree
5	Mathematics teachers leave the profession due to all of the above	2.94	.75	Agree	1.74	.67	Strongly Disagree

Table 4: Reasons mathematics teachers in secondary schools leave the teaching profession by mathematics teachers (N=254)

S/N	Item Statement	Public School Math Teachers			Private School Math Teachers		
		Mean	Standard Deviation	Decision	Mean	Standard Deviation	Decision
1	Mathematics teachers leave the profession due to retirement	3.02	.53	Strongly Agree	.41	1.25	Disagree
2	Mathematics teachers leave the profession due to resignation	2.68	.99	Agree	3.10	.84	Strongly Agree
3	Mathematics teachers leave the profession due to irregular and poor remuneration	2.98	.66	Agree	3.51	.60	Strongly Agree
4	Mathematics teachers leave the profession due to transfer of service	2.66	.70	Agree	1.89	.74	Strongly disagree
5	Mathematics teachers leave the profession due to all of the above	2.97	.72	Agree	1.74	.81	Strongly Disagree

Table 3 shows why mathematics teachers in secondary schools leave the teaching profession as responded by public and private secondary school principals in Nsukka Education Zone. The analysis shows that the public school principal agreed that mathematics teachers leave the profession due to retirement, resignation, irregular and

poor remuneration, and service transfer. They equally agreed to all of the above reasons as responsible for mathematics teachers leaving the teaching profession. On the other hand, principals of private secondary schools disagreed that all of the above reasons are responsible for mathematics teachers leaving the teaching profession. They disagreed that mathematics teachers leave the profession due to retirement and service transfer. However, they agreed that resignation and irregular and poor remuneration cause mathematics teachers to resign or leave the teaching profession. Therefore, the reasons that cause mathematics teachers to leave the teaching profession in public secondary schools include; retirement, resignation, irregular and poor remuneration and transfer of service. Whereas, in private secondary schools, the reasons that cause mathematics teachers to leave the profession include resignation and irregular and poor remuneration.

Table 4 shows the reasons mathematics teachers in secondary schools leave the teaching profession as responded by the public and private secondary schools' mathematics teachers in Nsukka Education Zone. The analysis shows that public school mathematics teachers agreed to leave the profession due to retirement, resignation, irregular and poor remuneration, and service transfer. Whereas mathematics teachers in private secondary schools disagreed that the above reasons are responsible for their leaving the teaching profession. The mathematics teachers disagreed with the item statements that they leave the teaching profession due to retirement and transfer of service. However, they agreed that resignation and irregular and poor remuneration caused them to resign or leave the teaching profession. Therefore, the reasons that cause mathematics teachers to leave the teaching profession in public secondary schools include; retirement, resignation, irregular and poor remuneration and transfer of service. Whereas, in private secondary schools, the reasons that cause mathematics teachers to leave the teaching profession in public secondary schools include; resignation and irregular and poor remuneration.

Research Question 5: Does the number of qualified mathematics teachers in the public and private secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone differ?

Table 5: Percentage of qualified mathematics teachers in public and private secondary schools

S/N	Qualifications	Public School MT		Private School MT	
		No. of MT	% MT Qualified	No. of MT	% MT Qualified
1	NCE	12	7	18	19
2	B.Sc.(Ed.)	122	76	64	69
3	MED	16	10	8	9
4	PhD	11	7	3	3

Table 5 shows the percentage of qualified mathematics teachers in public and private secondary schools in the Nsukka Education Zone. The analysis shows that out of the 161 mathematics teachers in the public secondary schools in the Zone, 7% have NCE,

76% have B.Sc.(Ed.), 10% have MED, and 7% have PhD. Of the 93 mathematics teachers in private secondary schools, 19% have NCE, 69% have B.Sc.(Ed.), 9% have MED, and 3% have PhD.

Figure 3: Chart showing the difference between qualified mathematics teachers in public and private secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone.

Figure 2 shows the difference between qualified mathematics teachers in public and private secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone. The chart reveals little difference in qualified mathematics teachers in Nsukka Education Zone’s public and private secondary schools.

Table 6: Mean difference between qualified mathematics teachers in public and private secondary school

Item	School Type	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean Difference
Qualified mathematics teachers	Public	161	1.16	.65	0.01
	Private	93	0.96	.64	

Table 7: t-test analysis of qualified mathematics teachers in public and private secondary school

School Type	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	t	df	p	Decision
Public	161	1.16	.65	2.425	252	.473	Not significant
Private	93	0.96	.64				

Table 6 shows the mean difference between qualified mathematics teachers in public and private secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone. The analysis indicates that qualified mathematics teachers in public secondary schools have a mean of 1.16 with a standard deviation of .65. In contrast, qualified mathematics teachers in private secondary schools have a mean of 0.96 with a standard deviation of .64. Their mean difference was 0.01. Hence, the mean of qualified mathematics teachers in public secondary schools is higher than the mean of private schools qualified mathematics teachers, with a mean difference of 0.01.

Hypothesis: Difference does not exist between qualified mathematics teachers in the public and private secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone.

Table 7 shows the t-test analysis of qualified mathematics teachers in public and private secondary schools in the Nsukka Education Zone. The table revealed that a difference does not exist between qualified mathematics teachers in the public and private secondary schools in the Zone, $t(252) = 2.425$, $p = .473$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was not rejected at $p > .05$ since it was not significant.

6. Discussion

The findings revealed the number of mathematics teachers required or demanded by the public and private secondary schools in relation to the number of teachers who retired or left the teaching profession in the Nsukka Education Zone between 2016 and 2021. However, the average number of mathematics teachers supplied to public and private secondary schools (170, 72) in the Zone does not match the average number of mathematics teachers demanded (820, 449). This imbalance of shortfall of mathematics teachers could lead to overstressing the teachers already in the system and could affect students' academic performance in mathematics. This lays credence to the findings of Shittu and Olubor (2021), Iyimo and Ishola (2018) and Njau (2017), who, in their respective studies, found that the demand for teachers does not commensurate with the supply, considering the increase in students' enrolment.

Findings also revealed that the average mathematics teacher-student ratio in the public and private secondary schools (1:234, 1:298) between 2016 and 2021 in Nsukka Education Zone is high. This could only lead to students' lack of concentration in the classroom and mathematics teachers being overburdened with a workload which might cause poor efficiency in mathematics delivery, among others. The results corroborate those of Thomas and Mbwas (2014), who looked at the quantity and quality of secondary school mathematics teachers. Their research on the teacher-to-student ratio revealed that, on average, it was 1:233, which is far too high. The results, however, go against recommendations made by UNESCO and the Federal Government of Nigeria (2013) in her National Policy on Education that the teacher-student ratio in secondary schools should be 1:40. Hence, the government and the private system should do more by employing more qualified mathematics teachers to bridge the gap.

The findings revealed the reasons mathematics teachers in secondary schools leave the teaching profession as school principals and mathematics teachers of public and private secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone responded. Mathematics teachers leave the teaching profession in public secondary schools due to retirement, resignation, irregular and poor remuneration and service transfer. In private secondary schools, mathematics teachers leave the profession due to resignation and irregular and poor remuneration. The government and the private school system would have to do more by motivating the mathematics teachers by raising their salaries to match their workload. That way, it could discourage them from leaving the profession through resignation. The government and the private school system would also have to employ more qualified mathematics teachers to reduce the workload they face in the Zone drastically. The findings support the findings of Njau (2017), who discovered a shortage of science and maths teachers in government secondary schools due to a lack of motivation, resignation and retirement. The findings also corroborate the results of Nwakonobi and Obiagwu (2010), who found that teachers leave the teaching profession due to transfer of service, retirement, poor salary and resignation.

The findings revealed little difference between the number of qualified mathematics teachers in public and private secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone. The hypothesis further tested this finding, revealing that a difference does not exist between the number of qualified mathematics teachers in the Zone's public and private secondary schools. This only means qualified mathematics teachers abound in the public and private secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone. However, what is left for the government and the private school system is to create an enabling environment and to employ more qualified mathematics teachers to meet the needs of students in the Zone.

7. Conclusions

The findings from this study revealed that the supply of mathematics teachers in public and private secondary schools does not commiserate with the demand for mathematics teachers in the Zone. Consequently, this study has established that the average mathematics teacher-student ratio in the Zone's public and private secondary schools is 1:234 and 1:298, respectively. The study has also established that mathematics teachers leave the teaching profession in public secondary schools due to retirement, resignation, irregular and poor remuneration, and service transfer. Whereas, in private secondary schools, the reasons mathematics teachers leave the teaching profession due to resignation and irregular and poor remuneration. Lastly, the study established that a difference does not exist between the number of qualified mathematics teachers in the public and private secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone.

8. Limitation

This study is not without limitations. The instrument was a questionnaire, so respondents may not have been entirely sincere in their responses. Therefore, using structured interviews would have provided more insight into the findings. Again, since this study was limited to Nsukka Education Zone, the results may not be transferable to other Education Zones of Enugu State.

Educational and Skill Planning Implications

This study reveals a considerable shortage of qualified mathematics teachers, implying that effective mathematics teaching might not be occurring in the Zone's public and private secondary schools. The high average mathematics teacher-student ratio has negative implications, such as general indiscipline among students and lack of concentration, leading to poor mathematics performance and overburdened teachers who may become less efficient.

Addressing these issues requires skill planning focused on recruiting and training more qualified mathematics teachers. This includes investing in teacher training programs, incentivizing careers in mathematics education, and enhancing pre-service and in-service training initiatives. Retention strategies are also crucial and may involve improving working conditions, offering competitive salaries and benefits, providing professional development opportunities, and implementing policies to support teacher well-being and job satisfaction.

Furthermore, the study highlights the need for policies and interventions to reduce class sizes and improve teacher-student interactions, thereby enhancing learning outcomes in mathematics. Ongoing research and monitoring efforts are essential to assess the effectiveness of these initiatives and adjust strategies as needed. Policymakers should collect and analyze data on teacher supply, demand, and retention rates to make informed decisions and ensure a sustainable and skilled workforce in the education sector.

Additionally, further studies should be conducted in various contexts, such as other Education Zones, to explore why mathematics teachers leave the profession and what could contribute to their retention in the school system. This study, being the first of its kind in Nsukka Education Zone in Nigeria, addresses significant gaps in understanding and offers guidance for effective skill planning and improved mathematics education.

9. Recommendation

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were proffered;

A huge gap exists between mathematics teachers' supply and demand for public and private secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone. Hence, the government and managers of the private school system should employ more qualified mathematics teachers to meet up with the recommended teacher-student ratio of 1:40. That way, the overburden of mathematics teachers engaging large crowds of students would reduce, which translates to more efficiency in the part of the teachers and performance improvement on the part of the students in mathematics.

The government and those driving the private secondary school system should create an enabling teaching environment for mathematics teachers and make the teaching profession financially attractive, especially by motivating and boosting mathematics teachers' salaries to reflect the current economic situation. That way, mathematics teachers resigning abruptly from the school system would reduce.

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